

International call for CCES post-doctoral positions

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The Center for Computing in Engineering & Sciences conducted at the end of March an international call for postdoctoral fellowships financed by the São Paulo Research Foundation (Fapesp). Further calls will be conducted in the next months. More information can be found at: <http://cces.unicamp.br/opportunities>.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2653128

The Center for Computing in Engineering & Sciences of the University of Campinas (UNIAMP) is devoted to the development and application of advanced modeling methods for the solution of frontier challenges in science and engineering, requiring high performance computing.

<http://cces.unicamp.br>

The center is funded by the São Paulo Research Foundation – FAPESP

CCES Researchers: New post-doctoral positions are available

Project: 2013/08293-7

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Editor: Leandro Martínez

Opportunities for post-doctoral researchers were open at the CCES in March. Diverse areas of computer science and its applications in Physics, Chemistry, Biology, and Engineering are covered.

The fellowships are for immediate start with a 2 year duration, with possible extension to 5 years. Furthermore, the researcher might develop one year of research in a partner CCES research institution in another country.

The selected candidates will work in an multidisciplinary environment, with high performance computing assuming a central role in every activity.

In the international call of March, more than 60 applications were received, from candidates of many nationalities. The candidates were selected based on their curricula and their adequacy to the projects to be developed.

The fellowships are available in the following major research areas:

- Towards data infrastructure for the CCES: Inquiry on Data Science and Semantic Interoperability.
- Machine learning methods for engineering and sciences.
- High performance FPGA accelerators for applications in science and engineering.
- Efficient migration of high performance computing science and engineering applications to the cloud.
- Programming models for High-Performance Cloud Computing.
- Integrated multi-omics analysis for biotechnological applications.
- Prospecting biomass-degrading enzymes using metagenomics and protein modeling approaches.
- Modeling of biomolecular and other heterogeneous materials.
- Multi-scale modeling of carbon nanomaterials and metal organic frameworks.
- Large-scale computing and statistical analysis of unsteady flows involving transition and turbulence.
- Large-scale computing in science and engineering.

Within each area, many projects are available. The projects will be developed in collaboration with two or more researchers of the CCES from distinct areas of knowledge.

New calls will be open in the next months!